

EVALUATION APPROACHES FOR OUT COME BASED EDUCATION

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Abstract

Evaluation is the process which determines the level of understanding on a specific course by an individual. Traditional evaluation methods adopted by majority of the higher educational systems in India focus mainly on theory examinations at the end of the course and based the marks scored by an individual. But such systems have failed in really measuring the outcome of a given course. These days where outcome based education has been getting popular among the higher education systems, institutions needs to adopt new evaluation strategies so as to measure the outcome of a given course by an individual. Various evaluation approaches could be considered during the course time mainly, Entry Test, Summary Sessions, Presentation assignments, Case study along with Application of the course concepts by using available software tools. This paper will discuss on these evaluation processes and also correlate its results on the outcome of a given course.

Keywords: Evaluation, Outcome Based Education, Entry Test, Summery Sessions, Case Study.

1. Introduction

Course Design is the process by which the raw data about a learning need is interpreted in order to produce an integrated series of teaching-learning experiences. Presently majority of the institutions among themselves stressing more on outcome based education. For the successful implementation of an outcome based education one needs to design the course accordingly and also system need to adopt a suitable evaluation practice to full fill such outcome based education[8]. Over a period, evaluation process is a traditional method by making students face examination at the end of the course period. Based on the individual's performance in the examination at the end of the course, students learning outcome will be estimated by correlating to his marks. But such systems fail in measuring the outcome of a given course, as majority of the students could able to reproduce the course content without actually knowing the course content. Thus evaluating the students based on marks obtained at the end of the course period can no more reflect the course outcome. Hence, institutions need to adopt some new approaches during the course period to evaluate as well as measure the outcome of the course. New evaluation approaches like Entry Test, Summery Sessions, Case Study, Presentations, Participatory Learning and Application of Software Tools, etc. need to be considered and it has to be done continuously over the course period[9].

2. Limitations with Traditional System

The traditional evaluation methods like examination at the end of the course will finally results with students memorising the course contents rather than getting knowledge. Two or Three hours of examination will lead to judge a student's ability under set conditions and limited time[8]. Many cases a student who actually good may get anxious and confused under because of strict exam conditions and fail to perform better in terms of scores. Faculty as well as students will be sticking to a curriculum focussed on passing or aiming to get high score in a specific exam. This will limit the curriculum to a set range of knowledge and skills and such practice does not provide educational benefits. The faculty will have his eye on the examination, and his teaching will be more of coaching in nature and finally fails in making the students apply their mind. Students, rather than assimilation of knowledge, concentrate more on reproducing course content.

3. Entry Test

This is an assignment to the students to know about the sessions content in advance to the class session. It has been found that sessions will be of more effective if the students attend with little ground working about the session topic. This helps the students to have some base knowledge on the session topic. In addition, these practices help in building interest among the students on the session topic and ultimately improve the knowledge gain. Hence, the faculty should adopt this practice by giving the next sessions topic in each session and asking the students to come with little home work on the given topic. At the beginning of the session, if a test is given to students by means of a quiz and record the performance of each student. At the end of the course period, these performances can be compiled, and it provides a basis for continuous evaluation of a student. This also improves the knowledge base among the students community.

4. Summery Sessions

Similar to the entry test discussed in section three, at the end of the session a summary test can also be considered by the concerned faculty. This summary test should covet major portions of the current session and measure the learning out come of the session. This also can be easily carried by means of conducting a quiz or MCQ method. Such performance also needs to be compiled, and it also can be a basis for continuous evaluation of the student. In addition, it improves the learning outcome among the students community.

5. Case Study and Presentations

Case study and Presentations will help in developing the students learning out come as well as their presentation and communication skills. By assigning independent case studies among the student community, individual students are made to learn about a given company or product or any special scenario in the real world. This makes the individual students to know more details about the given case and come up with detailed facts about the given case. By making him to present the case study among the group of audiences, one can improve on his presentation as well as communication skills. Performance of the students in these case study needs to compiled by the faculties and it also makes a basis for measuring the learning out of a course.

6. Participatory Learning

Participatory Learning is a process where in a student is made to involve in some activities that will improve the knowledge base among the student community. At the institution level various activities and events can be conducted under the student leaderships. This will make the student learn about the event management aspects and develops leadership skills. Various groups among the students can be formed and they are made to work in team to coordinate among each team. Faculties have to encourage students participations in such kind of events and their performance needs to consider as a basis for outcome evaluation.

7. Application of Software Tools

In case a course concepts are made to apply on available software tools, then it will greatly improve the learning outcome of that course. This method will make the student actually understand the course content and apply it on some available software tools. For example courses on Networks can be made to deploy over some simulation tools like GNS3, NCTUns[9] or Routerism[10] etc, then students will learn more on that course and it gives them some hands on experience. Similarly, a course on E-commerce is deployed using WordPress tool, then it makes the students better equipped with course concepts rather than a traditional method of class room teaching. More courses need to be designed as of this kind by the faculty team and students performance needs to record periodically. Compiled students performance on usage of such software tools will serve the basis to measure the outcome of the given course by an individual student.

8. Conclusion

Evaluation of a student is a process of assessing the level of learning outcomes on a given course which needs to be carried out on a continuous manner during a course period. Traditional evaluation methods like theory examinations at the end of the course and the marks scored by an individual student cannot be a good scale to measure the learning outcome on that course. A proper evaluation has to be done on the continuous basis throughout during the course period by adopting various methods as discussed in this paper. It has been found that practices like Entry Test and Summary Sessions will greatly improve the learning outcome of given course. Case Study and Presentations will result with additional knowledge gain in addition to improving the overall presentation skills. Participatory Learning approach will greatly improve the learning outcome on a given course apart from building the team work. Application of course concepts using some available software tools will give hands on experience to students which makes the course more interesting and also improves the learning outcome.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hutchinson, T and Waters, A. English for Specific Purposes. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- [2] Basturkmen, Helen. (2010). Developing Courses in English for Specific Purposes Basingstoke: Macmillan.
- [3] Widdowson H. G. Learning Purpose and Language Use Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- [4] HOLMES, J. 'Some Approaches to Course Design', Working Paper, Brazilian ESP Project.
- [5] Robinson, Pauline. ESP TODAY: A Practitioner's Guide. UK: Prentice Hall International
- [6] Dudley Evans, Maggie, Jo St John. Developments in English for Specific Purposes: a multi disciplinary approach. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- [7] Ronald Mackay and Alan Mountford. English for Specific Purposes. London: Longman.
- [8] Subrahmanya Bhat & Dr. K. R. Kamath (2018). Course Design Approaches for Outcome based Education, Proceedings of National Conference, Srinivas University.
- [9] Subrahmanya Bhat, & Dr. K. R. Kamath. (2016). Effective Learning With Usage of Simulators – A Case of Nctuns Simulator In Computer Networks. International journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, I (I), 415-420. ISSN-2455 – 5630.
- [10] S.Y. Wang and K.C. Liao, "Innovative Network Emulations using the NCTUns Tool," as a book chapter of the "Computer Networking and Networks" book, ISBN 1-59454-830-7, published by Nova Science Publishers
- [11] Subrahmanya Bhat, & Dr. K. R. Kamath. (2018). Exploring the Different Avenues of Network Parameters in Nctuns Simulator, Proceedings of National Conference, Srinivas University.